

POLITICAL SCIENCES

POLAND'S LEADERSHIP POLICY IN EASTERN EUROPE

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Abstract

The article examines the dynamics of socio-economic and political processes among the countries of Eastern Europe, the dominant feature of which was the Russian-Ukrainian war. Considering the fact that the Republic of Poland has been a strategic partner of Ukraine for a long time in the implementation of Ukrainian European integration and Euro-Atlantic aspirations, issues of bilateral dialogue and cooperation within the framework of the "Eastern Partnership" are revealed. Attention has been drawn to the fact that Warsaw's openness to Ukraine is consistent with Poland's existing ambitious plans to gain its own leadership in the region. Sensible intentions of increasing regional competition became more tangible after the coming to power in 2023-2024 of new political forces both in Poland and in the Czech Republic and Slovakia. The rapid dynamics and nature of changes prompt Ukraine to a balanced dialogue with the countries of the region on the military, economic and political components of security and the search for new formats of cooperation in order to achieve the declared national goals.

Keywords: Republic of Poland, European integration and Euro-Atlantic course, "Eastern Partnership".

Introduction

Formulation of the problem. The indisputable fact of today is that the modern transformations of the new model of the world system are determined by the main centers of power – the superpowers and their allies. Their goals, priorities and tasks change according to the requirements of time and dynamic parameters of the international environment. The scientific and technological revolution, global challenges and threats, the arms race, mass migration, aggravation of environmental problems, economic instability and pandemics – all this affects the politics of world players.

The background of global instability increases the ineffectiveness and weakness of existing international organizations and the reluctance of individual countries to act together in accordance with the declared goals and adopted decisions. Today, such a behavioral palette is vividly demonstrated by both UN member states and permanent members of the UN Security Council. However, the biggest challenge for the world community was the war of the Russian Federation (RF) against Ukraine. With its beginning the world order showed its weakness, and most importantly, the prospects of not being repeated on the "old basis" and within the limits of the declared rules of the game of the "stronger" world politics.

Undoubtedly, this nature of the course of world events did not pass by the decisions of "big politics" and influenced the revision of national development strategies "National Security Strategies" by many countries. It is clear that the security of borders, values and way of life was in the center of attention of these documents. Poland did not miss this issue either which in May 2020 recognized the Russian Federation as the main threat to the security of the state in accordance

with its new "National Security Strategy". Warsaw intends to implement the new "Strategy" through "leadership" and friendly relations with neighboring countries within the updated toolkit of the already familiar "Eastern Partnership" project.

The relevance of the research topic is determined by the following factors:

- 1) the need to clarify the potential of regional and international organizations in resolving conflict situations;
- 2) the need to clarify the foreign policy strategy of the Republic of Poland (RP) and the prospects for its materialization (strategy) in the format "Poland is a regional leader in Eastern Europe";
- 3) the need to clarify the main external and internal threats that affect both the implementation of the plans of RP in Eastern Europe as a whole, and cooperation with Ukraine in particular.

The purpose of the study is to determine the prospects and possibilities of the Republic of Poland becoming a regional leader in Eastern Europe.

Research methods. The methodological basis of the research is based on the fundamental principles of scientific knowledge such as historicism, systematism and objectivity. This study is based on a synergistic approach to the study of the historical stages of the development of the Republic of Poland taking into account the influence of external and internal factors, qualitative and quantitative methods of analyzing the military-political situation and the economic state of the state. The set of methods provided an opportunity to analyze and understand the political sphere of the Republic of Poland as a dynamic, non-linear system that is under the influence of various factors and external forces.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

Modern scientific works on aspects of the history and modern politics of the Republic of Poland have most wide a palette. For example, V. Skibitskyi, M. Duman-ska, O. Shevchenko, P. Wandych, O. Duleba, and O. Korol carried out thorough research on the geo- and foreign policy of Poland. Scientific articles by N. Buglai, S. Filimonov, N. Romanyuk, and D. Skvortsova on the issues of Poland's relations with NATO and the EU are of interest. The foreign policy of the Republic of Poland, its relations with the leading states of the world community, neighboring countries, including Ukraine are considered in the works of L. Zashkilnyak, D. Skvortsova, V. Khymynets, A. Shevchenko and other scientists.

Presenting main material.

The analysis of scientific publications, monographs, specialized publications and scientific articles that touches on the topic of the regional leadership of the Republic of Poland shows that the assessment of the situation in a separate region was, first of all, based on the analysis of the system of military-political relations between the countries of the region, the identification of existing and hidden contradictions between them and determining the real or potential status of individual states. In accordance with this provision the study of the situation in Eastern Europe is determined by the nature of the relations between the countries of the region, interstate organizations (unions, blocs) which include the Republic of Poland, taking into account the weight of the world power centers and the interests of the leading countries of the world which directly affects the situation and the formation of a leading position one or another country.

In general the military and political situation at the regional level (Eastern Europe) was assessed in the article in several stages, namely:

Stage 1 – determination of the impact of historical changes in the Republic of Poland in view of its foreign policy aspirations;

Stage 2 – determination (clarification) of the strategic importance of the position of RP in the region;

Stage 3 – development trends and forecasting of the military-political situation in the region, as well as determination of the position of the Republic of Poland in Eastern Europe.

The history of Polish statehood shows that it is expedient to talk about the formation of a coherent and self-sufficient concept of foreign policy in Poland only starting from the period that followed the end of the First World War. This period was associated with the restoration of the lost in the second half of the 18th century Polish statehood. At the same time it should be noted that there was no documentation of the concept of foreign policy in the Republic of Poland until 2012 inclusive [1, c. 70].

The second half of the 20th century was characterized not only by the rapid growth of technical and scientific progress, but also by the rapid change of ruling systems including in European countries most of which left their colonial ambitions and focused on solving social problems and security issues. Poland did not remain aloof from these transformations. After the end of

the Second World War the Polish United Workers' Party (PUWP) came to power in Poland which transformed it into the Polish People's Republic (PPR) under the protectorate of Moscow. This time in Polish history is positioned as an "anti-democratic communist dictatorship" and a period of "inefficient economic system".

It was the economic stagnation, the shortage of basic goods, the lack of political freedoms and free media, as well as the abuse of power by representatives of the political elite that provoked a series of protests that were suppressed by the communist authorities. So, for example, in December 1970, due to the increase in the prices of food, industrial goods and construction materials, protests arose in the northern cities of the Republic which were brutally suppressed by the communist leadership of the state. During mass actions, according to official data 45 people died, another 1,165 were injured [2].

In the specified period a trend of resistance to the communist government began which was embodied in waves of protests and their devastating suppression which in turn created the prerequisites for the formation of the labor movement as the basis of the specified trends in opposition to the government. The "Movement for the Protection of Human and Citizen Rights", "Student Solidarity Committees", "Committee of Peasant Self-Defense", "Movement of Young Poland" are considered to be the leading movements that managed to take active actions [3, c.134]. These movements have operated under the leadership of supporters of democratic traditions in public life, such as T. Mazovetskyi, B. Geremek, K. Modzelevskyi, Ya. Kuron, A. Michnik and others.

As Polish historians state already in the 1970s Polish society, one of the first in the countries of the Eastern Bloc, aspired to democratic changes, obtaining civil rights and freedoms.

It was guided by these aspirations and the request of Polish society for changes, the mentioned leaders of the resistance movement created an organized underground to overthrow socialism in the Polish Republic which led to the seizure of power [3, c.136], as a result of which Edward Gerek was elected the first secretary of the Central Committee of the Polish People's Liberation Army. It was E. Gerek who became one of the first leaders of the state who started a movement towards a market economy trying to update it by obtaining large loans from more developed Western countries. And although he managed to stabilize the situation for a while, economic stagnation began again in the early 1980s. As a result of the rapid deterioration of the economic situation and the growth of foreign debt to 27 billion dollars [4, c.104] the Republic of Poland is engulfed in a new economic crisis, which is turning into a wave of organized strikes. As a result of these riots the largest independent trade union "Solidarity" was created, headed by L. Valensa. In the future "Solidarity" turned into the center of all the democratic forces of the Republic of Poland which numbered more than 10 million people [5].

The political crisis, an unsustainable economic model, the attraction of the Polish population to democratic values and the observance of freedoms and rights necessitated fundamental changes in the system of state leadership. A big step on the way to such changes was the holding of a “round table” in February–April 1989 the result of which was the abolition of the leadership role of the People’s Party, the restoration of the bicameral parliament and the institution of the presidency the holding of early elections to the Seimas, as a result of which the democratic party won a convincing victory Solidarity [6, c.129].

Thus, after the parliamentary elections the next decisive step for the development of a democratic and leading Poland in its political and economic changes was the formation of the government of T. Mazowiecki who took a clear course to build a parliamentary democracy and transition to a market economy.

The main directions in which the new economic policy was implemented were the elimination of state control over prices, the attraction of foreign capital and the privatization of state property which in itself was very unusual for the eastern region. Thanks to such a new and decisive economic course in 1993 the Republic of Poland managed to get out of the crisis, reduce inflation and stabilize the national currency. Further changes in the economy demonstrated both positive trends and some shortcomings of “shock therapy”, and in the future gave the state the opportunity to retain a decisive role in regulating the development of the economy. The expansion and flexible use of both old and new market levers, such as money, credit, interest, made it possible to prevent large-scale criminalization of the economy and power, as well as significantly mitigate the social consequences of reforms [7]

In general the revolution of 1989 and the market mechanisms introduced by it gave a huge impetus to the development of the Republic of Poland as an independent, democratic state with a promising market economy. It was the first revolution in Central and Eastern Europe which was the result of a social movement in the state during which changes took place by reaching agreements between the ruling communist elite and representatives of the opposition. The events of 1989 contributed to the establishment of the third Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth the transformation of the Polish People’s Republic into the Republic of Poland with the rule of democratic order, freedom of speech, the formation of new, democratic bodies of state power, independent courts, strong and full-fledged territorial self-government, as well as a strong and developed market economy. These facts became the foundation of the country’s further success, the formation of its ambitious goals and the construction of a road map for achieving these goals which in turn bring the Republic of Poland closer to the position of a regional leader.

Joining NATO (March 12, 1999) as the main foreign policy priority was defined by the Republic of Poland already at the time of its gaining full state independence at the end of the 1980s. In March 1990 the Republic of Poland and NATO started official relations. With the adoption in November 1992 of the “Basics of the Polish Security Policy” and the “Security and

Defense Policy of the Republic of Poland”, the very idea of the country’s integration into the North Atlantic Alliance was officially declared, and it remained relevant throughout the following periods. Among the main factors that led to the aspirations of the Republic of Poland to join the union, it is necessary to highlight the historical circumstances associated with the post-war division of the world into two opposing camps and the subordination of the Republic of Poland to the Kremlin’s policy. For more than forty years the Republic of Poland was a member of the collective security system led by the Soviet Union. With the liquidation of the Warsaw Pact Organization (July 1, 1991) and the collapse of the USSR (December 25, 1991) the Republic of Poland like other states of Central and Eastern Europe faced the threat of being in a security vacuum surrounded by a stable democratically oriented Europe on the one hand and disintegrated post-Soviet space – from the other. Under such conditions it was forced to take responsibility for her own safety. The Republic of Poland was actually deprived of an alternative: in order not to be included again in the sphere of influence of the Russian Federation, in order to link security guarantees with integration into the Alliance [8]. In light of the above the accession of the Republic of Poland to NATO is rightly considered as an escape from the Russian Federation.

It should be noted that the Republic of Poland’s choice of a course to integrate into NATO was also conditioned by the unification with Germany, the experience of relations with which, similar to relations with the Russian Federation, testified to the existence of a potential danger for the Republic of Poland to be turned into a bargaining chip in the politics of the great neighbor. Placed between two geopolitical giants capable of absorbing it in order to satisfy their own great power ambitions, the Republic of Poland could not ignore the risk of repeating the sad scenario of 1939. Avoiding the development of events in this direction and preventing the transformation of Poland into a “battlefield” between the West and the East, according to the general opinion of the Poles, seemed possible only under the cover of a reliable shield, the role of which could only be fulfilled by the North Atlantic Treaty Organization. O. Kwasniewski in his first presidential speech emphasized the fact that NATO is the most powerful military and political structure in the world and it must be reckoned with [9].

The USA played an extremely important role in prioritizing the choice of the Euro-Atlantic course of the RP. Placing a “bet” on the American presence in Europe, the Republic of Poland considered it a guarantee of protection against Russian and German threats.

As the experience of the RP testifies, from the first democratic parliamentary elections in the early 1990s and throughout the following years, all political forces, from the left to the right demonstrating their commitment to the ideas of Euro-Atlanticism and Natocentrism understood Euro-Atlantic integration as “the only and appropriate way to ensure economic, military security and social development”, so this direction of the foreign policy of the RP remained unchanged [10].

Warsaw Government managed to achieve the first successes in building relations with NATO in the first half of the 1990s: at that time the state joined the North Atlantic Cooperation Council (NAC) (December 1991) and the Partnership for Peace Program (January 1994) and the political contacts at the highest level and the exchange of visits with the authorized representatives of the Alliance have become somewhat systematic. Although no specific statement was made regarding the prospect of the Republic of Poland joining NATO, the laid foundation determined the future success of the Republic of Poland.

It is necessary to emphasize the fact that an important stage in the implementation of NATO standards is the transformation of the defense-industrial complex. On December 14, 1995, the Ministry of National Defense was established as the central body of state defense management in order to manage the processes of reforming the defense sector. In the interest of fulfilling the planned, in June 1998 the "Program of integration with the North Atlantic Treaty Organization and modernization of the armed forces of the Republic of Poland for 1998-2012" was adopted, which contained a detailed plan for the renewal and technical reequipment of the Polish army for the next 15 years (note that the specified document currently updated every 5-10 years depending on needs and external threats).

Therefore, since the announcement of the course for integration and joining NATO the implementation of the Euro-Atlantic choice has always remained the main priority of the foreign policy of the RP the pragmatism of which, despite a number of challenges has never been questioned. The opening of the negotiation process is connected with the intensification of the RP's policy of promoting cooperation with NATO in the mass media. This experience of conducting information and educational work on explaining to citizens the expediency of joining the Alliance, as well as the guarantees that the state will receive after joining the Union can be useful for Ukrainian society as well. Marked by hard work to achieve union standards the country's accession to NATO was possible both thanks to the successes achieved in this area which undoubtedly proved the purposefulness of official Warsaw, its ability to solve difficult tasks in the political, military and legislative spheres, and thanks to consistent lobbying national interests at the level of the USA and the leading states of

Western Europe. The awareness of the Polish people of their europeanness, and at the same time the desire to establish themselves in the political discourse of Europe, to establish themselves as an influential subject of the system of international relations, in addition to integration into NATO and the EU (May 1, 2004), was manifested in the establishment and subsequent deepening of relations with leading states of the continent, first of all Germany. So, back in the early 1990s, choosing, given the geopolitical location, between orientation to the East or the West, Moscow or Berlin, the "buffer" between which the Republic of Poland had to be the Warsaw government made a choice in favor of the German capital.

In accordance with the acquisition of RP membership in NATO and the EU the main directions of foreign policy were declared: assistance to the eastern neighbors in the development of relations with the institutions of the Euro-Atlantic space, support of the forces fighting for democracy and de facto independence from the Russian Federation, expansion of cultural and civilization influence on the post-Soviet states, activation of cooperation with by Poles in emigration, formation of a positive image of the state in Europe and the world and others [10, p. 6]. Such a policy designed by preventing the resuscitation of the geopolitical dominance of the Russian Federation in the post-Soviet space and in the region of Eastern Europe, to ensure a significant strengthening of the position of the Republic of Poland in the spirit of its inherent "messianic pragmatism", according to experts, fully replicated the "Pax Americana", only on a smaller scale. In this, according to A. Malgin, the Republic of Poland "found the high-way of effective European political and economic self-identification" [10].

It should be noted that even without being a member of the European Community, as early as 2002, the Republic of Poland took the initiative of the "Eastern Dimension" policy which was supposed to become an effective mechanism of interaction between the EU and the countries of Eastern Europe where Poland was supposed to act as a mediator. However, at that time it did not receive proper support and was not put into practical use. Accordingly, with the accession of the Republic of Poland to the EU the opportunity for this turned out to be obviously better, and already in 2008, such an initiative – "Eastern Partnership" (date of creation - May 7, 2009) – appropriately formalized in cooperation with Sweden – was submitted to the Council of the EU for consideration, and in 2009 it became the official strategy of the community in relations with Ukraine, Moldova, the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Georgia, the Republic of Armenia and the Republic of Azerbaijan. Positioning itself as a state that has a long tradition of relations with its neighbors in the East, and therefore is well acquainted with their cultural, historical and mental traditions, the Republic of Poland, on its own initiative and in agreement with Brussels, thus turned into the main promoter of their interests in the EU is maximally involved in strengthening their democratic traditions, building civil society, and most importantly, deepening cooperation with the EU with subsequent accession to it. At the same time, through the guardianship of the "Eastern Partnership", the Republic of Poland got the opportunity to reanimate the main milestones of the Jagiellonian paradigm [10].

It is with such initiatives that the Republic of Poland is trying to find its unique place in the EU, to take the position of a leader among the countries of Eastern Europe and to prove that the state's place is among the elite of international politics. Performing the role of a mediator, the RP to a certain extent tries to concentrate the levers of influence on EU policy in relation to the countries of the region in its own hands. At the same time, having the "status quo" as an arbiter between the EU and the countries of Eastern Europe, the Republic of Poland can potentially use its position to achieve its

own interests and to some extent to impose its policies on the states in the region.

However, at the current stage being a full member of the EU the RP does not abandon its declared goals and ambitious plans. A certain independence and focus on one's own interests when making political decisions leads to aggravation of relations between the Republic of Poland and other EU countries. First of all, it concerns the interests of Germany, Hungary and Slovakia.

Summarizing the above, it should be noted that the Republic of Poland was interested in the expansion of the EU and integration into this European institution, and the opportunities for the accession of the Republic of Poland to the EU appeared after the collapse of the socialist bloc and the actual political and socio-economic transformation of the state. This was due, first of all, to the social demand for the democratization of society, the desire to obtain the rights and freedoms of a citizen, and on the other hand, to ensure one's own security. Ultimately, the achievement of the integration goals of the RP became possible thanks to the consistent policy pursued by the state leadership and the reforms necessary to gain membership in international organizations. Therefore, both the population of the state and the political leadership of the country saw in the integration into the European and Euro-Atlantic structures an opportunity to show the world their historical belonging to Greater Europe, to the Western world.

By integrating into the EU the Republic of Poland not only initiated the creation of the "Eastern Partnership" itself, but is also trying to form a group of its supporters in the EU. Strengthening its position the RP began to use its influence to support this project.

The aggressive policy of the Russian Federation during the last 15 years, and later the full-scale invasion of Russia into Ukraine, has forced Warsaw to review the vectors and strategy of national development and critically consider the activities of many international organizations.

Factors in the deterioration of relations between the West and the Russian Federation, such as the annexation of Crimea, the war in Ukraine, anti-NATO rhetoric, etc., have given Poland's leadership reasons to consider itself the next potential target. And this despite the fact that Poland is under the protection of Article 5 of the Treaty on the Collective Security of NATO Member States.

The above mentioned changes in the geopolitical situation observed in the world and in Europe in particular, as well as the status of Poland as a potential territory of probable conflict between the Russian Federation and NATO, have contributed to the adoption and active implementation of the Plan for the Modernization of the Armed Forces of the State until 2026.

According to the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Poland M. Blaschak, the Plan envisages spending a record \$48.9 billion in the next six to seven years. In 2019 Warsaw has allocated \$2.91 billion for the implementation of the plans in the future funding for the modernization of the army will increase and in 2025 will amount to \$6.85 billion [11].

Warsaw's implementation of this Technical Modernization Plan by 2030 will allow Poland to become a regional leader in the military sphere with the most numerous and modern army in Europe.

In view of the aggravation of the military and political situation in the Eastern region of Europe Poland has been also forced to rethink its foreign policy goals of cooperation for the future. According to the statement of the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Poland Zbigniew Rau in April 2023 before the Polish Sejm, the aggressive policy of the Russian Federation remains the biggest threat to peace in Europe including the security of Poland. Currently, the Republic of Poland is building and strengthening regional formats of cooperation by developing ties and strengthening the appeals of our region around the world, primarily within the framework of the European Union and NATO [12, p.18].

The minister noted that first of all the goals of future cooperation concern the Three Seas Initiative (date of creation – January 16, 2024), the task of which is to harmonize the economic development of our region throughout the EU. Poland will strive to make the Three Seas Initiative an institutional flywheel that will become the driving force behind Ukraine's post-war reconstruction – a process that should take place in parallel with EU accession, i.e. the expansion of appropriate infrastructure ties. For this reason, the RP also sees Romania and Bulgaria advancing to the Schengen area (date of creation - March 26, 1995) quite quickly.

Z. Rau noted that the "Eastern Partnership" the initiator and leader of which was the RP in the European Union prepared Ukraine and Moldova for EU accession – for candidate status. Regarding Ukraine the RP will strive to give it the opportunity to join such structures of the free world as the European Union and NATO as soon as possible [12, c.33].

It should be noted that NATO is not the only attribute of the Polish defense strategy, as the state seeks to intensify cooperation in the field of security between EU member states which according to official Warsaw, can best be represented by the implementation of the EU's Common Security and Defense Policy (CSDP), as well as any other forms of multinational defense initiatives on a European scale. One of the examples of such an initiative in the field of defense can be the creation of the joint Lithuanian-Polish-Ukrainian brigade "LITPOLUKRBRIG" named after the Great Hetman Kostiantyn Ostrozky.

It should be noted that the progressive nature of the development of Ukrainian-Polish cooperation is, first of all, determined by the coincidence of the national interests of the neighboring countries in many areas, their deep historical and cultural ties. The state of international cooperation between the Republic of Poland and Ukraine is characterized by high intensity. Active work is being carried out at the level of permanent institutional mechanisms of bilateral interaction, dialogue is being conducted regarding the search for new and improvement of already existing forms of cooperation [13]. The Polish side pays special attention to supporting Ukraine's European course. The Republic of

Poland became one of the first countries to sharply condemn the invasion of Russian troops into Ukrainian territory and the annexation of Crimea [10]. The Polish leadership is in favor of providing Ukraine with international support, as well as material, financial, and military-technical assistance from the EU, NATO and the IMF. As part of this policy Warsaw has developed a plan of measures aimed at supporting reforms in Ukraine in the administrative, security, economic, financial, judicial, humanitarian and educational spheres.

The policy of the Russian Federation in relation to neighboring states forces Poland to intensify and deepen cooperation in the field of security and defense, primarily within the framework of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization and at the level of bilateral relations, primarily with the USA. It is the close ties with the USA that to a certain extent “untie the hands” of the Republic of Poland in relations with the EU and member states of the union. Having ensured its security, the Republic of Poland is trying to achieve the role of one of the leading political countries in Europe. Poland is beginning to express its ambitions by opposing the policy of member states and the EU itself in certain issues. Such aggravation of relations to some extent provides an impetus for the development of foreign policy relations of the Republic of Poland within the framework of other initiatives, projects and platforms. Examples of such initiatives can be “Visegrad Union”, “Mizhmorya”, “Three Seas”, “Eastern Partnership”. It is the creation and participation in the mentioned projects that enables the Republic of Poland to take the position of a leader, an independent, strong player capable of uniting other states around itself.

Participation in such international organizations as the EU and NATO opens perspectives for the Republic of Poland that allow the state to realize its ambitions now and in the future. Through political organizations, for example, the “Weimar triangle” (date of creation – 1991), the Republic of Poland aspires to take a place among the top three EU countries in the future. With regard to regional cooperation in Eastern Europe, the Republic of Poland conducts its own policy and increases its political influence through such organizations as the Visegrad Four (established on February 15, 1991) and the Eastern Partnership.

By implementing its own projects and projects of international organizations within the framework of such initiatives as “Three Seas” and “Mizhmorya”, RP gets the opportunity to take the position of a political leader in the region in the long term. After all, if we hypothetically consider the possibility of Poland leaving the EU or the possible disintegration of the EU due to existing external and internal factors, the very use of these initiatives and projects can in the long run create a basis for the Polish state to unite the countries around it into new economic unions or military political blocs.

In recent years, due to the military invasion of the Russian Federation in Ukraine Poland has undergone the biggest changes in the defense sphere among the countries of Eastern Europe. With the assistance of the United States, as well as in accordance with the Action Plan to increase NATO’s combat readiness the Eastern flank of the Alliance is being strengthened due to the

placement of the advanced command post of the divisional level of the US Army Ground Forces which was moved from the territory of Germany to the Republic of Poland, the headquarters of NATO’s high readiness forces, as well as an additional military contingent on the territory of the Republic of Poland. At the same time Russian aggression forces the Republic of Poland to actively modernize its armed forces. That is why the Ministry of National Defense of the Republic of Poland adopted and is already actively implementing the Plan for the Technical Modernization of the Armed Forces until 2035. Official sources of the Ministry of Defense make ambitious statements that by 2032 the Armed Forces of the Republic of Poland will be one of the most modern and numerous in all of Europe [14]. Given the above, it can be predicted that the implementation of this Technical Modernization Plan by 2030 will allow the Republic of Poland to become a regional leader in the military sphere with the most numerous and modern army in Europe. The specified modernization plan and the pace of its implementation will potentially strengthen the eastern border of both the state itself and the NATO bloc giving the Polish state a special status in Europe as a whole.

Ukraine considers the neighboring Polish state as one of its main strategic partners in the implementation of Ukraine’s European integration and Euro-Atlantic aspirations through active bilateral cooperation, fruitful cooperation within the framework of the “Eastern Partnership”.

Conclusions

1. The security of the foreign policy of today’s Republic of Poland which has an influential historical background in view of the long tradition of state-building. The democratic revolution of 1989 gave a huge impetus to the development of an independent and democratic Republic of Poland with a market economy. The Republic of Poland became the first revolutionary country in Central and Eastern Europe which took place as a result of a social movement and fundamental changes, which were implemented by reaching agreements between the ruling communist elite and representatives of the opposition. The events of 1989 contributed to the formation of the Third Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, the transformation of the Polish People's Republic into the Republic of Poland on the basis of democracy, freedom of speech, independent courts, strong and full-fledged territorial self-government, and a market economy.

2. Warsaw’s desire for regional leadership can be considered a leading geopolitical goal of Poland which is based on the desire to expand its political influence through coalition expansion on neighboring states. The available indicators of influence and economic development, in turn testify to the real prospects of acquiring this status. But it is precisely this active activity of Polish politicians that provokes the emergence of “reverse” external factors and factors that affect the dynamics of the implementation of ambitious plans.

3. The prospect of Poland becoming an Eastern European leader looks achievable and real. By setting ambitious goals, Warsaw skillfully lobbies for its own

interests at all political levels and international platforms, uses the mistakes and failures of others, and also transforms its own weaknesses into new opportunities for the state.

4. The war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine determines the urgent need for Ukraine to intensify its foreign policy activities taking into account its own national interests. Taking into account the weight of Poland in making political decisions within NATO and the EU, Kyiv should actively use this resource of Warsaw in the “war for duration” and create favorable conditions for defending its own national interests in the future.

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